

Bridging the Gap in the Educational Neglect of Girl Children

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Introduction

Girl children and Adolescent girls are exploited throughout their lives. Since time immemorial girl children are abused, neglected and their rights are always ignored, rather denied. In India, girls are always confined to domestic work like bearing children and caring the family members. But times are changing fast in urban areas of our country due to modern education and awareness of the gender equality. Gender disparities are common in rural areas. In this situation we can bridge the gap through proper education on the rights of girl children for education health and sustainable development.

Objectives of the Paper

1. To analyze and assess the existing gap in education support to disadvantaged girls for development.
2. To find out the means to improve the educational support in various educational institutions, so that gender disparity eliminated.
3. To refer the millennium development goals about child development and improve the support.

Educational Neglect-Present Condition

In a family law context, “Educational Neglect” refers to a parent’s failure to provide for a child’s basic needs with regards to school and education. In most cases, this refers to younger children who are still claimed as dependents of the parent. It can also include any adult who is legally responsible for the child, such as a stepparent, legal guardian, or custodian of the child. Educational neglect is often classified under child abuse and neglect laws.

For an adult to be held liable for educational neglect, it needs to be proven that the parent has failed to provide an education for the child that is consistent with state requirements. Thus, educational neglect laws may vary depending on the family and education laws in each particular region.

Education neglect generally implies the parent’s failure to perform certain duties on behalf of the child and their educational needs.

These can include:

1. Failing to ensure that the child receives proper educational care and attention
2. Failing to enrol the child in school
3. Allowing the child to continually miss school, be delinquent, or truant
4. Deliberately interfering with the child’s educational development

In some states, educational neglect only applies to children of a certain age, which is generally from the ages 7-14 (the ages may vary by state). Also, there may be separate neglect provisions that specifically address children who are being home-schooled. Strategies for overcoming educational neglect

We can overcome the above difficulties by educating our children, Parents, Teachers through awareness ICT, Social media etc., Social media place a vital role in shaping our society. Girl children are always over exploited in the media. This should be prohibited. Some of the steps needed are given below

Fundamental Rights of Girl Children

Human Rights are universal, and civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights belong to all human beings, including children and young people. Children and youth also enjoy certain human rights specifically linked to their status as minors and to their need for special care and protection. Girl-children are particularly vulnerable to certain human rights violations, and therefore require additional protections.

The human rights of children and the girl-child are explicitly set out in the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the most widely ratified human rights treaty in history. They are also contained in other human rights documents including the Universal Declaration, the Covenants, CEDAW, and other widely adhered to international human rights treaties and Declarations.

Girl’s Education and Millennium Development Goals

The millennium development goals have targeted eight key areas - poverty, education, gender equality, child mortality, maternal health, disease, the environment and global partnership. Each goal is supported by 21 specific targets and more than 60 indicators.

These goals are to be translated into Tamil language and distributed in all schools, colleges and other educational institutions educate our educational authorities.

Audio-Visual will help in achieving the MDG Goals among student community.

Social Media Today

Girl children today have been given too much of liberty either parents in both urban and rural areas. Usage of cell phones has spoiled students community in our country. Social media like Facebook have become platforms for wrong paths and thousands of girl children are exposed to pornography and sexual exploitation. For example the recent sexual abuse (POLLACHI ISSUES) of girl children through Facebook has shocked the entire Tamilnadu. Four youngsters have spoiled the life hundreds of girls who are on facebook. The misuse of Facebook should be restricted by parents, teachers and all concerned.

Another case which challenged the safety of women in the country surfaced in Tamil Nadu. The Tamil Nadu police arrested the kingpin of a gang which used to blackmail women on pretext of sharing their videos on social media. The police arrested the leader of the gang.

The man was arrested for sexually assaulting several girls and then blackmailing them. The accused allegedly used to threaten girls by telling them that he would share their videos on social media. The accused used to blackmail girls for money and sexual favours.

Bridging the Gap-Conclusion

1. Families of disadvantaged girl children should be requested to give necessary support and guidance instead of dropout in schools.
2. Sponsorship programmes should be encouraged for basic education, medical care and continuous education.
3. You are enabling effective implementation of education provisions for girl’s rights and empowerment of poor girls from marginalised society to ensure gender-responsive environment.
4. Dropout in schools should be minimized with the help of teachers and parents.
5. Educational neglect in school should be thoroughly analysed so that various support programmes for the full development of girl children are worked out.
6. Girl children in orphanages and homes should be strictly monitored so that child abuse, exploitation, child trafficking will be eliminated.
7. Regular awareness programmes on girls rights should be conducted in schools in rural areas with participation of parents of girl children. Audio-visual shows will be very effective.

Web Sources

1. <https://www.legalmatch.com/law-library/article/educational-neglect.html>
2. https://www.pdhre.org/rights/women_girl_child.html
3. <https://www.theguardian.com/global-development/datablog/2015/jul/06/what-millennium-development-goals-achieved-mdgs>